

Why Do We Need New Leadership Styles in Today's Organizations?

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Abstract: *Why do today's organizations need new leadership styles? This is an emerging fact that dynamic organization requires a dynamic leader to run the organization effectively as well as efficiently. Moreover, the organizational dynamic environment creates the movement around the Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP). This paper examines through the relevant literatures on leadership and leadership theories to generate the new leadership styles for organizational need. Theoretical construction was drawn from the leadership theory. The findings and discussions on this conceptual paper reflect on leadership style that focuses on the components of Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP) which was indicated as the Followers, the leaders and the organizational context. This paper elaborates on the leaders and follower's flexibility and mobility to gain ground on new leadership approaches. The gaps were identified on the Situational leadership theory on the components of leader and followership domain. This paper illustrates the theoretical construction and discusses the flexibility and mobility of both the leader and the followership in an organization, which today's organization needs for running effectively, efficiently and for success.*

Keywords: Leader; followers; Followership; leadership; factor of organizational productivity; theory; flexibility; mobility; leadership readiness

Introduction

In this dynamic era, moreover with the COVID-19 post pandemic situation, dynamic leadership styles have become means of necessity to run today's organization. Dynamic leadership and dynamic environment generate dynamic movement to all *Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP)*. This *Factor of Organizational Productivity (FOP)* can be categorized into three aspects, *The Followers, The Leaders and The Organizational context*.

However, if any one of this *Factor of Organizational Productivity (FOP)* remains stagnant, it can slow the momentum of pace towards smooth and efficient running of organizational operations. For example, a static follower "*never to change attitude*" who most often seek to their comfort zone are the status quo group, these segments of followers require to be instigated to motivate for change for dynamic context that is possible with the dynamic leadership, so does a dynamic followership domain "*always determined to adapt change*"

attitude” towards contextual variations who often desire for the dynamic leadership styles. If in case any of these factors of organizational productivity remain stagnant it essentially requires stimulation and this is possible through dynamic leadership styles. Moreover, Green (2016) states that the dissatisfaction among the employees affects the organizational productivity. It is the leaders’ job as one of the major components of Factor of Productivity to enrich the resources within the organizational culture to enhance both the organizational performances and the followers’ motivations. Al-Tit (2017) suggests that both the organizational culture and organizational resources have a significant relationship with the organizational productivity.

All these *Factor of Organizational Productivity* (FOP) are the circle of organizational operational activities, any static momentum can cause the organizational to fall back and this in turn can take massive effort to stand often to compete with the speedy dynamic environment in today’s world.

Leadership is not all about bringing changes, it is however all about adapting to the changes and creating the environs for the followership to adapt within the changing environs, and importantly, creating a harmonious climate within current change contexts. Thus setting the new and improvised organizational behavioural settings that were experienced from both the dynamism of internal and external environmental forces. Leadership is essential also to gear organizations towards the dynamic movement to meet the quality of social working life and to remain readiness and become future-oriented. However, Atkinson and Mackenzie (2015) admit that effective leadership can bring changes by initiating towards goal direction and motivating the employees.

Leadership Dynamism and Factor of Organizational Productivity

Dynamic movement of environments and Factors of Organizational Productivity requires leadership readiness. Rajbhandari, (2015) and Rajbhandari, et. al. (2014) critically examined the Situational Leadership Theory (SLT) and indicated flaws within the leadership styles on the part of leadership readiness. Although follower’s readiness was measured in the SLT, leadership readiness was missed-out that the SLT ignored to measure, which therefore needed to be rectified within the SLT to regenerate the vibe of leadership theory by adding up the 4th Dimension on the SLT. This 4th dimension of leadership furthermore, generated leaders from all around the world to practice leadership on themselves and not on the followership domain alone, despite the situational factors dictate the followers to measure their readiness and maturity level. In the original SLT developed by Hersey and Blanchard (1977) only 3 Dimensions were studied *The Situations, Followers and the Leader behaviors* were examined within 4 stages to illustrate the follower’s readiness.

Figure 1 Situational Leadership Model. Hersey and Blanchard (1977)

Figure 1. Source: Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari (2013). School Leadership En-route to ‘Grand Leap’ Case studies from Nepal and Finland. (p. 25).

An improvised theory to Situational leadership theory was proposed by Rajbhandari (2014) by adding up the 4th Dimensions to the SLT to complement to strengthen the leadership parameters of leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility, which was ignored to measure in the original theory of SLT. As the major component of factor of organizational productivity was totally ignored by the original Situational leadership theory and the gap of leadership readiness were identified (see figure 2), thus, leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility was totally an unexplored area on leaders’ part. In addition, the dynamic era, all factors of organizational productivity are dynamic, therefore, all these factors of organizational productivity need a new leadership style to pursue the organizational goal into the organizational mission and vision.

Figure 2. Source: Rajbhandari, M. M. S (2014). Critical perspective on Situational Leadership Theory. Leadership Readiness for Flexibility and Mobility. The 4th Dimensions on Situational Leadership styles in educational settings.

The Situational Leadership theory remained much popular for over 40 years until a critical perspective on leadership was closely examined. This generated a new paradigm of leadership thought in practice which appealed for the leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility. Moreover, in this article, another factor of Organizational productivity is also discussed, which is in line to the Followers readiness for flexibility and mobility. The important factor of the Followership domain remained stagnant and static during the exploration of developing the Situational leadership theory in 1974 by Hersey and Blanchard. The dynamism of leadership and followership both require the readiness for flexibility and mobility. Therefore, followership readiness for flexibility and mobility is also an essential ingredient to complete the Situational Leadership theory along with the leadership readiness. If any one of these factors of Organizational Productivity is stagnant and is in static movement, the Situational Leadership theory cannot support the contextual variations, thus, failing the whole process in the organizational settings.

In the figure 2, the dotted arrow signifies the gap of leadership approaches towards flexibility and mobility. These gaps were not being identified in the original theory of situational leadership. However, this it is important for the leaders to remain flexible according to the followership domain. This is because, not all followers within the followership domain are equally capable of reaching the equal maturity level at once.

Although, Situational leadership theory indicates the four paradigms of followership domain, which are telling, selling, participating and delegating, these four domains are not flexible and mobile. The theory assumes stagnant movement, whereas, in the dynamic world, the stagnant movement and assumption of step-wise maturity level of all followers are not possible with only two leader's behaviour (Relations and task-orientations). Nevertheless, it is a dynamic leadership inheriting the flexibility and mobility according to the need of the context and the followership domain that can initiate the followership domain towards flexibility and mobility.

Discussions and conclusion

Moving forward with the need of leadership flexibility and mobility, the original theory of situational leadership also ignored to indicate the followership flexibility and mobility. The original theory indicated that followership movements within the four paradigms are stagnant and moves from one stage to another via a system process manner. In reality and in this dynamic organizational life, both leadership and follower's readiness for flexibility and mobility are required and is necessary for the organization to grow in the competitive world of business and management.

Moreover, context that relates to external environs are difficult to change, however, context that relates within the organization can be managed to change. This requires daunting task from the leadership domain. In this connection, the *Factor of productivity* (FOP) which

generally contains the components of leaders, followers and the organizational context can all be changed, provided the context relates to the organizational internal environs.

In the figure 3, the dotted and the highlighted lines with the number indicated are the leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility. The readiness of leaders flexible and mobile nature can boost organizational productivity. However, the major component is not the leadership domain alone, it is equally important to understand that followership domain contains the vast majority of people led by one or few leaders. Accordingly, with line to followership maturity level, leaders need to act upon to distinguish the real and actual maturity levels that are existing within the followership domain. Therefore, by practicing the leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility, it is also required that each individual in the followership domain are ready to move to the next stages of maturity level. It is in fact that not all followers within the followership domain contain the equal capability of possessing the same level of maturity level as other followers. In this regard, even the followership needs to be readily flexible and mobile.

The organization gains in productivity if all factors of productivity are progressed equally, nevertheless, this is rarely practicable in the dynamic world of today. It is also necessary that followers not only move to the next level as directed or supported by the leader's behaviour but it is important to see if the readiness for maturity of the followers are not competent to move forward, the readiness towards being flexible and mobile to move from all stages are necessary for the organizational productivity to flourish.

The bold circle dotted line indicates the follower's domain towards readiness for flexibility and mobility (Fig 3). Within the internal environ, if the factor of Organizational Productivity is constant to change, to adopt the organizational changes towards development and growth, the improvised theory situational readiness theory of followership and leadership can gain much important values to the organizational leaders, followers, thus, enhances to enrich the factor of organizational productivity within the organizational lives.

The theory of Situational Readiness of followership and leadership not only increases organizational performances, but will and can change to enrich the harmonious organizational climate within the organizational setting. This is achieved by creating social and goal-oriented bonds between and amongst the organizational resources that further increases the values within the factor of organizational productivity.

Likewise, the internal context that plays an important role to shape the organizational commitment, performances, productivity, can be played with organized deployment of organizational resources where and when necessary. This can be further done by evaluating the followership domain with their readiness of maturity level and their nature of flexibility and mobility akin to leadership readiness for flexibility and mobility. Therefore, readiness for changes is important in any area of organizational lives.

Figure 3. Situational Readiness of followership and leadership flexibility and mobility

The above figure scientifically and academically indicates to demonstrate new leadership of 4th dimension on leadership style by exerting the leaders “Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competences and Intelligence (SAKCI)” (Rajbhandari, 2016, 2017) to match with the followership domain and the follower’s maturity and immaturity level readiness for flexibility and mobility for organizational effectiveness. The thick dotted circle is the followership readiness for flexibility and mobility which is an additional aspect related to the Factor of Organizational Productivity that is highly essential for organizational effectiveness.

Therefore, any factor of organizational productivity remaining static can hamper the organizational efficiency, its effectiveness, and development to meet with the future demand.

In conclusion, today’s organizations need to value almost every component that attach to the organizational social lives. Moreover, time management is the most expensive components that can be wasted by offering less useful training expectant on the development of human resources within the organization for the outcome of organizational effectiveness. It has been essential within organizational behaviour to enrich the human social factors through research

and development with rigorous scientific methods. These aspects that develop the organizational social lives are always missing therefore, failing to enrich the quality of social working life amongst and between the employees and peers within the organizational environs.

Dynamic organizations need dynamic leadership and followership. These two factors of organizational productivity are complex. Furthermore, leadership and followership are even more complex to practice in general organizational environments. Nevertheless, to consistent effectiveness of organizational X-efficiency, (here X denotes an additional contributing factor to its relevant associating components), encouragement towards employees training within the framework of theories is important for further initiating their development towards bringing about dynamism changes associating to organizational changes. The reason for practicing theories in the workplace is essential. This is because, in Western Countries and in neighboring countries, theories have played a vital role in enhancing the organizational effectiveness in the dynamic changing environments. These theories practiced in the organization are developed from within the organizational framework by investigating on business/organizational managers, leaders and further provides training to employees through the basis of these developed theory.

Similarly, research and development at organizations, groups, and individuals' level in Nepalese organization has only been stagnant with report submissions. Reports and research are two different aspects and are not equivalent. Thus, researching within the organizational settings need to be encouraged by business organization, which however, need to be incorporated with the academic rigor and scientific methods, from which, in today's dynamic social environs, new and contextual leadership styles can be generated to match up with the existing organizational followership domain. This further enables organizational leaders to generate dynamic leadership styles to fit in the cluster of contextual variations such as different cluster of various followership groups within one organizational setting.

Moreover, it must be understood that one style of leadership in one organization may not fit in the situation of another organizations. Organizational context differs from one another and so does their organizational culture and climate. The issue remains, does harmonized organizational climate can bring about organizational effectiveness and X- efficiency? To briefly provide the glimpse to this issue, the practice of *Actions-oriented leadership style* (Rajbhandari, 2017) focusing on both relations and task is necessary. The simultaneous practices of Actions-oriented leadership styles, where applicable contextually can enable the effectiveness of organizations and achieve X-efficiency within the organization by bringing about social harmony within the organizational climate. Seidel (2015) admits that an individual work performance for X-efficiency is important for productivity of an organization.

Furthermore, instigation towards research in scientific manner and *theoractive learning* (Rajbhandari, 2011 and 2018) and training can generate flexible followership domain within and between the groups of followers further enabling them to adopt within the changing and dynamic organizational changes and development. Initiating for research, development and

training can nevertheless, effectively utilize the under-utilized and the unutilized human resources in an organization further enabling the organization to lead towards future and simultaneously maintain the harmonized Factors of Organizational Productivity (FOP).

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